

follicle stimulating hormone subunit beta (FSHB) : Time behavioural study of 3rd order combinations in WNT3A stimulated HEK 293 cells

shriprakash sinha

Independent Researcher; Orcid ID : orcid.org/0000-0001-7027-5788

Address : 104-Madhurisha Heights Phase 1, Risali, Bhilai-490006, India

Corresponding author email : sinha.shriprakash@yandex.com

Abstract

The pituitary glycoprotein hormone family includes follicle-stimulating hormone (FSH), luteinizing hormone (LH), chorionic gonadotropin (CG), and thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH). They all consist of an identical alpha subunit and a hormone-specific beta subunit. FSHB encodes the beta subunit of FSH. Along with LH, FSH induces egg and sperm production. Gujral and MacBeath [1] provides a quantitative, and dynamic study of WNT3A-mediated stimulation of HEK 293 cells, where they record time based expression profiles of several response genes which correlated significantly with proliferation and migration. By monitoring the dynamics of gene expression using self-organizing maps, they identified clusters of genes that exhibit similar expression dynamics and uncovered previously unrecognized positive and negative feedback loops. However, their study depicts/uses singular measurements of individual gene expression at different time snapshots/points to infer the system wide analysis of the pathway. At any particular time point, it is often the case that genes are working synergistically in combinations, even though their expression measurements are singular in nature. Here, I • enumerate and rank all 2415 FSHB related 3rd order combinations in a forest of ${}^{71}C_3$ combinations using four different sensitivity methods; • show the conserved rankings for FSHB-X-X combinations, which point to existence of biological synergy of some of these combinations across the different sensitivity methods; and • study the behaviour of some of these combinations related to WNT3A response genes that are ranked by the machine learning search engine (Sinha [2]) in time. Patterns of combinations emerge, some of which have been tested in wet lab, while others require further wet lab analysis.

Keywords: Sensitivity analysis, Support vector ranking, Hilbert Schmidt Independence Criterion indices (HSIC) and Sobol indices, WNT3A

[☆]Time behavioural study of 3-odr FSHB comb. in WNT3A stimulated cells

¹Aspects of unpublished work were presented in a poster session at Cell Symposia: Technology. Biology. Data Science, 9-11 October 2016, Berkeley, California, USA.

1. Significance

Sinha [2] recently demonstrated the use of machine learning based search engine to rank/reveal gene combinations at 2nd order for the time series data by Gujral and MacBeath [1] and showed how it is possible to locate combinations of priority that might be working synergistically, using sensitivity methods and powerful support vector ranking algorithm. However, the problem explodes combinatorially with even a small set of 71 recorded genes in the study by Gujral and MacBeath [1], when one steps to explore 3rd order combinations. With the total number of ${}^{71}C_3$ (= 57155) combinations, it becomes nearly impossible for any biologist to study the system wide dynamics of any pathway. Also, the amount of time usually needed to search for and test a combination is far more than the search down by the machine learning based search engine. Here, I extend the research work by Sinha [2] to conduct a behavioral study of 3rd order FRAT1 related combinations using individual gene expressions measured in time, in WNT3A stimulated HEK 293 cells.

2. Introduction

The details of the machine learning based search engine has been recently published in Sinha [2] and deployed to explore the 2nd order combinations of genes in the data set provided by Gujral and MacBeath [1]. Nevertheless, here, I point to the fundamentals of the published work for completeness.

2.1. A combinatorial problem

Sensitivity analysis plays a major role in computing the strength of the influence of involved factors in any phenomena under investigation. When applied to expression profiles of various intra/extracellular factors that form an integral part of a signaling pathway, the variance and density based analysis yields a range of sensitivity indices for individual as well as various combinations of factors. These combinations denote the higher order interactions among the involved factors. Computation of higher order interactions is often time consuming but it gives a chance to explore the various combinations that might be of interest in the working mechanism of the pathway. For example, in a range of fourth order combinations among the various factors of the Wnt pathway, it would be easy to assess the influence of the destruction complex formed by APC, AXIN, CSKI and GSK3 interaction. But the effect of these combinations vary over time as measurements of fold changes and deviations in fold changes vary. So it is imperative to know how an interaction or a combination of the involved factors behave in time and Sinha [2] develops a procedure to track the behaviour by exploiting the influences of these involved factors.

2.2. A possible solution

In this work, after estimating the individual effects of factors for a higher order combination, the individual indices are considered as discriminative features. A combination, then, is a feature set in higher order (≥ 2 , i.e. multivariate). With an excessively large number of factors involved in the pathway, it is difficult to search for important combinations in a wide search space over different orders. Exploiting the analogy with the issues of prioritizing webpages using ranking algorithms, for a particular order, a full set of combinations of interactions can then be prioritized based on these features using a powerful ranking algorithm via support vectors Joachims [3]. Recording the changing rankings of the combinations over time reveals how higher order interactions behave within the pathway and when an intervention might be necessary to influence the interaction within the pathway.

2.3. follicle stimulating hormone subunit beta (FSHB)

As recorded in Standring [4], the pituitary gland or hypophysis is an endocrine gland in vertebrates. It has two main lobes, namely, an anterior lobe, and a posterior lobe joined and separated by a small intermediate lobe. The anterior lobe (adenohypophysis) is the glandular part that produces and secretes several hormones. The posterior lobe (neurohypophysis) secretes neurohypophysial hormones produced in the hypothalamus. Both lobes have different origins and they are both controlled by the hypothalamus. Hormones secreted from the pituitary gland help to control growth, energy management, all functions of the sex organs, blood pressure, thyroid gland, metabolism, as well as some aspects of pregnancy, childbirth, breastfeeding, temperature regulation, water/salt concentration at the kidneys and pain relief. Glycoprotein hormones (GPHs) are the most complex molecules with hormonal activity. They exist only in vertebrates but the genes encoding their subunits' ancestors are found in most vertebrate and invertebrate species although their roles are still unknown. Cahoreau et al. [5] review the available structural and functional data concerning GPHs and their subunits' ancestors. Glycoprotein hormones (GPHs) are the most complex molecules with hormonal activity. The pituitary glycoprotein hormone family includes follicle-stimulating hormone (FSH), luteinizing hormone (LH), chorionic gonadotropin (CG), and thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH). They all consist of an identical alpha subunit and a hormone-specific beta subunit. FSHB encodes the beta subunit of FSH and along with LH, FSH induces egg and sperm production.

[6] analyzed a human genomic DNA fragment in phage λ containing FSHB, and determined the nucleotide sequence of the region of the clone encoding FSH β . Their analysis of a set of cell hybrids containing translocated derivatives of chromosome 11 further localized FSHB to the human chromosome region 11p11.2 \rightarrow 11pter. A Hind III restriction fragment length polymorphism (RFLP) detected by another subclone of the λ phage containing FSHB provided a genetic marker for this region of the human genome.

FSH, and the FSH receptor (FSHR), a G protein-coupled receptor, play central roles in human reproduction. Jiang et al. [7] reported the crystal structure of FSH in complex with the entire extracellular domain of FSHR (FSHR_{ED}), including the enig-

matic hinge region that is responsible for signal specificity. Surprisingly, they found that the hinge region did not form a separate structural unit, but was part of the integral structure of FSHR_{ED}. In addition to the known hormone-binding site, FSHR_{ED} provided interaction sites with the hormone: a sulfotyrosine (sTyr) site in the hinge region consistent with previous studies and a potential exosite resulting from putative receptor trimerization. Their structure, in comparison to others, suggested that FSHR interacted with its ligand in two steps: ligand recruitment followed by sTyr recognition. • FSH first binds to the high-affinity hormone-binding subdomain of FSHR and reshapes the ligand conformation to form a sTyr-binding pocket. • Next, FSHR inserts its sTyr (i.e., sulfated Tyr335) into the FSH nascent pocket, eventually leading to receptor activation.

Summarizing Ulloa-Aguirre et al. [8], Tao and Segaloff [9] and Simoni et al. [10], FSH (a gonadotropin) stimulates steroidogenesis and gametogenesis in the gonads, while being secreted by the anterior pituitary gland. It regulates the menstrual cycle and ovarian follicular maturation in women and supports sperm production in men, by binding to the FSH receptor (FSHR) on the granulosa cell surface in ovaries and the Sertoli cell surface in testes. The stimulated receptor leads to the dissociation of α - and $\beta\gamma$ - subunits of G protein heterotrimer inside the cell. The α -subunit activates adenylyl cyclase, resulting in an increase of cAMP levels, and ultimately leads to the increased steroid production that is necessary for follicular growth and ovulation in women, while the free $\beta\gamma$ dimers recruit G protein-coupled receptor (GPCR) kinases to the receptor, which, in turn, lead to the recruitment of β -arrestin to the receptor.

I present 3rd order combinations of FSHB with other genes, that the machine learning based search engine points to, as possible synergistic combinations that might be working in time.

3. Methods

Please refer to sections of Sinha [2] for methods, design of study and analysis of data for 2nd order combinations. The same method and design of study is used to generate results for 3rd order combinations presented in this study.

4. Time series data

Gujral and MacBeath [1] present a set of 71 WNT-related gene expression values for 6 different times points over a range of 24-hour period using qPCR. The changes represent the fold-change in the expression levels of genes in 200 ng/mL WNT3A-stimulated HEK 293 cells in time relative to their levels in unstimulated, serum-starved cells at 0-hour. Gujral and MacBeath [1] state that qPCR data are the means of three biological replicates. Only genes whose mean transcript levels changed by more than two-fold at one or more time points during the 24-hour time course were considered significant. Positive (negative) numbers represent up (down) -regulation. We have already covered the issues related to these data sets in detail in Sinha [11]. Readers are requested to go through them in the pointed reference. The tools of study which are used here have been published in another foundational work in Sinha [11].

5. Design of experiment

5.1. Pipeline for time series data

For the case of time series data, interactions among the contributing factors are studied by comparing triplets of fold-changes at single time points. The procedure begins with the generation of distribution around measurements at single time points with added noise is done to estimate the indices. A distribution is generated for the fold changes at single time points. Then for every gene, there is a vector of values representing fold changes as well as deviations in fold changes for different time points and durations between time points, respectively. Next a listing of all C_k^n combinations for k number of genes from a total of n genes is generated. k is ≥ 2 and $\leq (n - 1)$. Each of the combination of order k represents a unique set of interaction between the involved genetic factors. After this, the datasets are combined in a specified format which go as input as per the requirement of a particular sensitivity analysis method. Thus for each p^{th} combination in C_k^n combinations, the dataset is prepared in the required format from the distributions for two separate cases which have been discussed above. (See .R code in mainScript-1-1.R). After the data has been transformed, vectorized programming is employed for density based sensitivity analysis and looping is employed for variance based sensitivity analysis to compute the required sensitivity indices for each of the p combinations. This procedure is done for different kinds of sensitivity analysis methods.

After the above sensitivity indices have been stored for each of the p^{th} combination, the next step in the design of experiment is conducted. Since there is only one recording of sensitivity index per combination, each combination forms a training example which is allotted a training index and the sensitivity indices of the individual genetic factors form the training example. Thus there are C_k^n training examples for k^{th} order interaction. Using this training set SVM_{learn}^{Rank} Joachims [3] is used to generate a model on default value C value of 20. In the current experiment on toy model C value has not been tuned. The training set helps in the generation of the model as the different gene combinations are numbered in order which are used as rank indices. The model is then used to generate score on the observations in the testing set using the $SVM_{classify}^{Rank}$ Joachims [3]. Note that due to availability of only one example per combination, after the model has been built, the same training data is used as test data to generate the scores. This procedure is executed for each and every sensitivity analysis method. This is followed by sorting of these scores along with the rank indices (i.e the training indices) already assigned to the gene combinations. The end result is a sorted order of the gene combinations based on the ranking score learned by the SVM^{Rank} algorithm. Finally, this entire procedure is computed for sensitivity indices generated for each and every fold change at time point and deviations in fold change at different durations. Observing the changing rank of a particular combination at different times and different time periods will reveal how a combination is behaving.

Note that the following is the order in which the files should be executed in R, in order, for obtaining the desired results (Note that the code will not be explained here) - • use source("mainScript-1-1.R") with arguments for Dynamic data • source("SVMRank-Results-D.R"), to rank the interactions (again this needs to be done separately for

different kinds of SA methods), • use source("Combine-Time-files.R"), if computing indices separately via previous file, • source("Sort-n-Plot-D.R") to sort the interactions. Note that the sorting is changes the interaction ranking in time. Thus • use source("Interaction-Priority-Intime.R") to find the prioritized ranking of each and every interaction over the different time points and finally • use source("Print-Ranking-AND-Interaction-Rank.R") to print individual ranking of the required input factor with other interaction factors.

6. Results & Discussion

6.1. Time series data by Gujral and MacBeath [1]

NOTE - Ranking was assigned on scores that were sorted in DECREASING values. So, 1 was assigned to highest score and vice versa.

Results for the 3rd order interactions are presented here. The results first discuss the behaviour of interactions across the snapshots of time using the computed sensitivities on fold change measurements per time snapshot. The analysis was done using 4 different sensitivity indices. Out of the 7C_3 combinations, I consider/present only those combinations that show a ranking within first 10,000 out of 57,155. This choice is liberal and biologists/oncologists can have a more stricter choice as per need. Two observations are made, • the ranking of a particular combination is conserved (i.e within the 10,000 range) in a particular time point or in the early phase or late phase of WNT3A stimulation, across the majority of the four sensitivity methods, which is a strict criteria of assessment or • the ranking of a particular combination is conserved across time points/phase (i.e they are within the 10,000 range) and the majority of the four sensitivity methods, which is relaxed criteria of assessment. Applying this filter helps reveal important combinations of interest that might be working synergistically at a higher order level in the cell.

Regarding technical points of implementation, the rankings were generated without scaling/normalizing the time series data provided by Gujral and MacBeath [1]. For estimating the sensitivity indices, a small gaussian distribution using the function **rnorm** that generates a vector of normally distributed random variables given a vector length n (here 9, the 10th one is the mean/recorded gene regulation itself), a population mean μ and population standard deviation σ . The syntax for using rnorm is as follows: **rnorm(n, mean, sd)**. Further, I use the **jitter** function to add a little bit of noise to the data. This helps to see if the generated rankings are robust or not.

6.2. Enumeration and ranking of 2415 FSHB-X-X combinations from Gujral and MacBeath [1]

In the supplementary section, I present four files, each containing the rankings of 3rd order combinations, that vary in time (shown for 5 time points). Each file represents the rankings computed using a particular sensitivity method. The changing rankings in time for a particular combination represents the importance of contribution/role that combination plays in the cell stimulated with WNT3A. The sensitivity methods used

are Hilbert Schmidt Independence Criterion indices (HSIC) indices (with rbf and linear kernel in Da Veiga [12]) and Sobol indices (with 2002 implementation in Saltelli [13] and martinez implementation in Martinez [14] and Baudin et al. [15]).

6.3. Conserved machine learning rankings for tested FSHB-X-X combinations

A total of 2415, 3rd order combinations involving FSHB were obtained from a full set of ${}^71C_3 = 57155$ combinations. Further, from this selected set, using the above criteria for conserved rankings, I report/tabulate the meaningful combinations that might be working synergistically. Tables 2, 3 and 4 show the rankings for the same combinations as in table 1, but using rbf kernel for HSIC, 2002 implementation for SOBOL and martinez implementation for SOBOL, respectively. As one tallies the rankings of across these tables for a particular combination, one finds that the role of the combination of interest is conserved. This conservation points to the existence of the biological synergy, whether the combination has been tested or unexplored/untested.

6.3.1. GnRH regulates FSH

Gonadotropin-releasing hormone (GnRH) a decapeptide that is secreted in pulsatile fashion from the hypothalamus into the pituitary portal vasculature, regulates FSH synthesis and secretion (Bernard et al. [16]). Mason et al. [17] observe that the deletional mutation of at least 33.5 kilobases encompassing the distal half of the gene for the common biosynthetic precursor of GnRH and GnRH-associated peptide (GAP) causes hereditary hypogonadism in the hypogonadal (hpg) mouse. The partially deleted gene was found to be transcriptionally active as revealed by in situ hybridization histochemistry of hpg hypothalamic tissue sections, but immunocytochemical analysis failed to show the presence of antigen corresponding to any part of the precursor protein.

6.3.2. Examining the behaviour of JUN / TCF / LEF / CTNNB1 -FSHB-X combinations

GnRH is known to regulate gonadotrope function through a complex transcriptional network that includes three members of the immediate early gene family: EGR1, JUN, and ATF3. These DNA-binding proteins act alone or in pairs to confer hormonal responsiveness to CGA, LHB, FSHB, and GnRHr. Salisbury et al. [18] suggested that the transcriptional response of JUN required a functional interaction between the T-cell factor (TCF)/lymphoid enhancer factor (LEF) family of DNA-binding proteins and β -catenin (CTNNB1), a coactivator of TCF/LEF. Their supporting data include demonstration that GnRH increases activity of TOPflash, a TCF/LEF-dependent luciferase reporter, in $L\beta T2$ cells (a gonadotrope-derived cell line). Their additional cotransfection experiments indicated that a dominant-negative form of TCF7L2 (TCFDN) that bound DNA, but not β -catenin, blocked GnRH induction of TOPflash. Overexpression of AXIN, an inhibitor of β -catenin, also reduced GnRH stimulation of TOPflash. Transduction of $L\beta T2$ cells with TCFDN adenoviruses diminished GnRH stimulation of JUN mRNA without altering expression of EGR1 and ATF3, two other immediate

RANKING @ t_i USING HSIC - LINEAR

3rd order comb.	t_1	t_3	t_6	t_{12}	t_{24}	3rd order comb.	t_1	t_3	t_6	t_{12}	t_{24}
FSHB-T-WNT5A	122	29061	57139	24091	2613	FSHB-NKD1-PPP2R1A	134	11978	48147	4744	11658
FSHB-FZD2-SEN2	155	15792	56338	24860	16086	FSHB-FZD2-WNT4	180	18252	43713	35344	29882
FSHB-FZD2-PPP2R1A	216	20883	30530	35125	19903	FSHB-FZD2-FZD7	245	31877	48883	39603	50115
FSHB-T-WNT4	285	39661	52682	15922	9372	FSHB-FZD2-KREMEN1	286	34277	55693	24595	31187
FSHB-FZD2-TLE2	364	13058	45957	41222	23515	FSHB-FZD2-LRP5	366	26369	56367	45627	15311
FSHB-T-TLE2	387	33919	53269	21476	12396	FSHB-FZD2-SFRP4	413	14029	55048	31393	43835
FSHB-NKD1-TLE2	425	30274	24343	8644	12849	CSNK2A1-FSHB-SFRP4	494	33797	31035	11392	7911
CSNK1G1-FSHB-LEF1	506	19332	10676	684	44215	FSHB-LEF1-TCF7L1	545	41739	49954	24854	32409
CSNK1D-FSHB-LEF1	553	21733	36403	3295	16135	FSHB-NKD1-SEN2	574	7025	14205	7566	35992
CSNK1G1-FSHB-SFRP4	577	21679	6780	1575	25615	FSHB-T-TCF7	594	43385	15195	24841	22963
DKK1-FSHB-SEN2	641	24808	11118	11901	46995	FSHB-FZD2-FZD6	659	6508	55230	34443	24422
FSHB-NKD1-WNT2B	699	45757	26960	8191	17214	FSHB-LEF1-TLE2	716	51374	47443	17350	25939
DIXDC1-FSHB-LEF1	777	45272	10940	6689	22555	FSHB-GSK3A-KREMEN1	921	38254	26495	28443	3064
FSHB-FZD2-PPP2CA	922	15170	15248	37534	18116	FSHB-FZD2-TCF7L1	938	32749	50626	39797	16705
FSHB-NKD1-RHOU	974	40540	14067	9128	35039	FSHB-NKD1-SFRP1	1011	27987	21471	7065	1983
FRZB-FSHB-SEN2	1016	13136	7480	5202	23820	FSHB-FZD2-TCF7	1018	40516	45622	34770	44337
FSHB-T-TCF7L1	1029	40997	50899	17756	3833	CSNK1G1-FSHB-SEN2	1054	47479	13640	1228	8996
FSHB-GSK3A-SEN2	1073	16288	25162	18111	11005	FSHB-FZD2-LEF1	1118	14309	53366	39173	16692
FSHB-NKD1-WNT5A	1146	8921	29165	19619	2206	FSHB-FZD2-WNT5A	1190	10906	56570	47332	4072
FRZB-FSHB-SFRP4	1223	1819	11388	6342	54806	FSHB-LEF1-SEN2	1229	12578	50301	24457	7777
FSHB-FZD2-GSK3B	1266	6938	48999	24583	37158	FSHB-NKD1-TCF7L1	1387	37613	10650	8338	29279
FSHB-T-WNT2	1426	29977	55062	12965	5468	CSNK1G1-FSHB-PPP2CA	1518	8523	49087	1235	27660
DKK1-FSHB-LRP5	1519	2594	16842	22232	37962	FSHB-NKD1-TCF7	1528	46050	40792	9733	32939
CSNK2A1-FSHB-PPP2CA	1544	21794	56458	12205	17377	FSHB-FZD2-FBXW4	1577	20522	32605	35591	25593
CSNK2A1-FSHB-WNT2B	1655	8809	48217	20614	27385	FSHB-MYC-SEN2	1661	3841	29219	24971	7457
FSHB-FZD2-FZD8	1671	15948	53024	35438	29190	FSHB-FZD2-PITX2	1681	25060	56319	33266	14323
FSHB-FZD2-SLC9A3R1	1795	39694	55787	33593	41890	FSHB-FZD2-TLE1	2027	28569	54198	36983	37820
FSHB-LEF1-WNT4	2075	48049	40576	21210	20847	FSHB-FZD2-RHOU	2193	41442	55751	28895	48790
FSHB-T-WNT3A	2242	34175	56516	9226	7363	FSHB-GSK3A-PPP2R1A	2267	11196	31968	18565	24240
FSHB-FZD2-WNT3A	2298	5294	54044	44316	3638	CSNK1D-FGF4-FSHB	2441	17927	45150	34061	11599
FSHB-NKD1-WNT2	2558	23961	6398	3570	16109	FSHB-FZD2-SFRP1	2559	7953	55268	36582	36554
CSNK2A1-FSHB-FZD7	2601	20741	19320	11749	49197	FSHB-GSK3A-FBXW4	2618	22592	44503	22209	12645
FZD5-FSHB-SEN2	2620	37348	11372	8592	28360	FSHB-GSK3A-RHOU	2698	43462	34330	18933	10698
FSHB-FZD2-PORCN	2817	7691	52867	46696	28509	FSHB-MYC-TLE2	2923	22109	41704	26993	3530
AES-FOXN1-FSHB	2965	25071	19677	24885	18445	FSHB-MYC-FBXW4	2969	20328	49942	19643	3752
CSNK1G1-FSHB-MYC	2987	47541	16749	1201	23454	FSHB-FZD2-NLK	3007	15229	33503	42544	8088
DIXDC1-FSHB-FZD1	3136	45375	11211	11425	29794	FBXW11-FOXN1-FSHB	3234	11903	14136	23118	30110
DIXDC1-FSHB-T	3255	34040	47003	6560	49035	CSNK1G1-FSHB-WNT2B	3357	9060	28997	6593	37362
FSHB-PORCN-PPP2R1A	3420	9611	38143	42456	10626	CSNK2A1-FSHB-FZD1	3426	27759	33533	13224	35693
FSHB-GSK3A-WNT2B	3606	48867	25838	31124	32847	CSNK2A1-FSHB-SEN2	3609	22209	11628	8401	7649
CSNK1G1-FSHB-T	3636	19798	35345	312	15515	FOSL1-FOXN1-FSHB	3654	9548	17000	26396	39466
FSHB-NKD1-FBXW4	3657	26327	16817	8776	23172	CSNK1G1-FSHB-TLE2	3685	24521	6309	2390	53267
FRZB-FSHB-FZD1	3720	4368	14235	6831	35610	FSHB-FZD2-WNT2	3865	8188	47829	31525	37626
FSHB-GSK3A-TCF7	3904	42280	17499	22970	14161	FSHB-FZD2-MYC	3937	20248	51571	40207	23081
BCL9-FGF4-FSHB	3946	21353	21679	27526	39205	FSHB-LEF1-SFRP4	4021	45839	49234	24757	19506
FSHB-T-TLE1	4039	47213	53727	15401	29351	FRZB-FSHB-LEF1	4117	679	11864	4333	15549
CSNK1G1-FSHB-TCF7L1	4143	12682	12075	1247	30342	CSNK2A1-FSHB-TCF7L1	4195	17520	18854	11543	18761
CSNK1G1-FSHB-FZD1	4236	6426	15848	1850	51462	FSHB-JUN-SEN2	4244	14780	24139	39454	6681
CSNK2A1-FSHB-LEF1	4295	17954	29380	8714	37682	CTBP2-FOXN1-FSHB	4321	40069	14063	16057	55165
FSHB-LEF1-SLC9A3R1	4432	52834	53254	14595	12082	APC-FSHB-LEF1	4475	29086	10632	356	11132
DIXDC1-FSHB-TCF7L1	4549	31863	7056	10277	4669	FRZB-FSHB-LRP5	4578	8579	23418	10147	14329
FSHB-NKD1-WIF1	4621	8153	24750	5910	428	FSHB-GSK3A-WNT5A	4722	7262	52632	23091	38927
DIXDC1-FSHB-SFRP4	4856	39200	10508	10415	29896	CCND1-CTNBP1-FSHB	5004	56520	36248	44136	53863
FSHB-MYC-WNT4	5012	22216	28105	26520	25995	DVL1-FSHB-FZD1	5035	53508	16024	470	29060
FRZB-FSHB-PPP2CA	5204	19049	54010	6133	27813	EP300-FOXN1-FSHB	5265	2613	14431	12535	3811
FSHB-JUN-WNT4	5288	7708	26793	41418	20711	CSNK1G1-FSHB-LRP5	5322	17826	30783	6398	41762
CSNK1G1-FSHB-RHOU	5346	18138	12773	776	39643	FSHB-JUN-TCF7	5360	34303	50964	37006	36402
FSHB-FZD2-NKD1	5427	29500	40214	25746	8412	FSHB-PYGO1-WNT2	5434	16740	51092	5393	7521
CSNK1G1-FSHB-WNT2	5533	14900	6829	467	30316	FSHB-LEF1-MYC	5538	29950	53848	14480	13768
FSHB-MYC-RHOU	5540	30302	25407	22566	36470	FSHB-NKD1-NLK	5645	9268	38001	6547	21186
FSHB-PYGO1-WNT3A	5662	9149	57045	8437	25486	DAAM1-FOXN1-FSHB	5694	41648	33798	14726	32752
FBXW2-FSHB-FZD2	5712	39025	17476	10127	28195	CCND1-CTBP1-FSHB	5725	56748	29592	50558	40456
FSHB-JUN-LRP5	5767	3832	55208	46575	2660	CSNK1D-CTNBP1-FSHB	5796	33605	55368	17392	32696

Table 1: Rankings of FSHB-X-X. A list of approximately first 125 combinations with rankings below 10,000 out of 57,155. SA - HSIC; Kernel - linear

early genes that confer GnRH responsiveness. Reduction of β -catenin in L β T2 cells, through stable expression of short hairpin RNA, also selectively compromised GnRH regulation of JUN expression and levels of JUN protein. Finally, overexpression of

RANKING @ t_i USING HSIC - RBF											
3rd order comb.	t_1	t_3	t_6	t_{12}	t_{24}	3rd order comb.	t_1	t_3	t_6	t_{12}	t_{24}
FSHB-T-WNT5A	38699	15943	1093	25527	28563	FSHB-NKD1-PPP2R1A	25236	3206	25555	29398	54336
FSHB-FZD2-SENP2	722	17184	1804	8318	40473	FSHB-FZD2-WNT4	6816	11813	3438	4079	43595
FSHB-FZD2-PPP2R1A	10535	30086	26859	11239	24594	FSHB-FZD2-FZD7	4675	7640	5535	26749	20732
FSHB-T-WNT4	34987	32997	6654	22504	22222	FSHB-FZD2-KREMEN1	5444	42081	8565	25988	38407
FSHB-FZD2-TLE2	7557	9982	1122	7042	3191	FSHB-FZD2-LRP5	21769	12398	268	13884	19062
FSHB-T-TLE2	47144	33788	2346	14889	40413	FSHB-FZD2-SFRP4	4323	24559	5053	16811	10612
FSHB-NKD1-TLE2	17403	24824	7167	5397	44661	CSNK2A1-FSHB-SFRP4	17159	7039	55890	17829	49642
CSNK1G1-FSHB-LEF1	46458	5148	44690	1362	34271	FSHB-LEF1-TCF7L1	9166	53185	6306	4873	46442
CSNK1D-FSHB-LEF1	55374	14244	35230	8216	18460	FSHB-NKD1-SENP2	14879	5325	16207	3306	6877
CSNK1G1-FSHB-SFRP4	49673	9604	39425	16774	51741	FSHB-T-TCF7	15963	48634	1342	15324	3240
DKK1-FSHB-SENP2	13659	23744	54431	4021	33075	FSHB-FZD2-FZD6	983	15277	13285	3027	53066
FSHB-NKD1-WNT2B	24792	50507	25909	42911	36692	FSHB-LEF1-TLE2	17915	43860	1667	9288	40897
DIXDC1-FSHB-LEF1	56469	45507	52727	16153	8570	FSHB-GSK3A-KREMEN1	9218	45608	28535	37479	51895
FSHB-FZD2-PPP2CA	3195	15838	9446	3827	55246	FSHB-FZD2-TCF7L1	6008	50769	1291	19412	38941
FSHB-NKD1-RHOU	13620	39126	15440	38560	46234	FSHB-NKD1-SFRP1	28217	31095	6105	12696	47885
FRZB-FSHB-SENP2	5870	14328	41622	369	53440	FSHB-FZD2-TCF7	1081	40554	555	14927	53924
FSHB-T-TCF7L1	18421	44307	4524	7756	18690	CSNK1G1-FSHB-SENP2	41253	35360	30966	2443	33408
FSHB-GSK3A-SENP2	6015	32214	13032	15982	30339	FSHB-FZD2-LEF1	31623	27017	5219	9724	12888
FSHB-NKD1-WNT5A	45339	3228	1592	43013	28219	FSHB-FZD2-WNT5A	4908	10915	532	36402	27866
FRZB-FSHB-SFRP4	29574	11603	47383	3209	39274	FSHB-LEF1-SENP2	16486	20092	5835	4015	10968
FSHB-FZD2-GSK3B	1138	11606	9514	35386	46428	FSHB-NKD1-TCF7L1	29187	51071	22006	21070	31900
FSHB-T-WNT2	50362	19754	5809	18153	37120	CSNK1G1-FSHB-PPP2CA	50070	6934	23453	5427	21042
DKK1-FSHB-LRP5	17832	17573	35336	9068	54014	FSHB-NKD1-TCF7	16167	43862	3127	18402	9845
CSNK2A1-FSHB-PPP2CA	14473	24470	49869	6189	28547	FSHB-FZD2-FBXW4	7085	29857	30431	35123	20442
CSNK2A1-FSHB-WNT2B	14373	4327	52378	10457	6308	FSHB-MYC-SENP2	11261	1740	20872	3892	32896
FSHB-FZD2-FZD8	2194	10044	3079	38866	42600	FSHB-FZD2-PITX2	11301	38653	1373	55358	36056
FSHB-FZD2-SLC9A3R1	10325	37190	5991	25853	20686	FSHB-FZD2-TLE1	15519	25551	3634	38322	51551
FSHB-LEF1-WNT4	41497	39387	3625	9699	38711	FSHB-FZD2-RHOU	1282	37769	4155	7339	22181
FSHB-T-WNT3A	37189	29725	873	25128	8181	FSHB-GSK3A-PPP2R1A	2994	22740	47062	16574	48029
FSHB-FZD2-WNT3A	10002	6702	2404	44003	56141	CSNK1D-FGF4-FSHB	8876	10878	93	40281	25736
FSHB-NKD1-WNT2	18619	15105	23935	22810	37921	FSHB-FZD2-SFRP1	4118	5933	771	28595	38823
CSNK2A1-FSHB-FZD7	32789	11231	55533	29970	24990	FSHB-GSK3A-FBXW4	6890	34487	49297	34455	41976
FZD5-FSHB-SENP2	9883	31485	55203	2031	44565	FSHB-GSK3A-RHOU	10474	45128	43164	20106	41469
FSHB-FZD2-PORCN	2992	1901	452	19552	44544	FSHB-MYC-TLE2	13836	3400	17675	6625	31499
AES-FOXN1-FSHB	1721	19780	28544	48157	1579	FSHB-MYC-FBXW4	20928	25297	33253	38049	15480
CSNK1G1-FSHB-MYC	43747	46283	35580	1289	17413	FSHB-FZD2-NLK	17474	18226	16777	16181	28351
DIXDC1-FSHB-FZD1	3527	44586	55840	4528	2895	FBXW11-FOXN1-FSHB	6061	13017	20945	50606	93
DIXDC1-FSHB-T	36455	36262	54691	1183	12572	CSNK1G1-FSHB-WNT2B	43414	19138	41449	6694	6668
FSHB-PORCN-PPP2R1A	16061	9508	29505	10633	56512	CSNK2A1-FSHB-FZD1	14124	9142	52833	6616	46703
FSHB-GSK3A-WNT2B	7286	43548	39375	36993	48203	CSNK2A1-FSHB-SENP2	11122	26033	53443	288	43776
CSNK1G1-FSHB-T	51659	22786	44198	2191	56498	FOSL1-FOXN1-FSHB	11030	8091	27557	40910	3512
FSHB-NKD1-FBXW4	37869	19703	30672	38958	40988	CSNK1G1-FSHB-TLE2	37782	18462	30690	1164	44080
FRZB-FSHB-FZD1	9269	6036	46659	4923	47946	FSHB-FZD2-WNT2	7061	8112	4177	36695	20465
FSHB-GSK3A-TCF7	3290	46377	13521	12930	56685	FSHB-FZD2-MYC	29737	23746	2961	11852	18465
BCL9-FGF4-FSHB	19360	11815	11389	48533	47985	FSHB-LEF1-SFRP4	30991	41207	7433	5395	45348
FSHB-T-TLE1	20294	41198	2613	16496	22703	FRZB-FSHB-LEF1	54972	6560	43425	13496	36529
CSNK1G1-FSHB-TCF7L1	33263	14566	33778	3739	35177	CSNK2A1-FSHB-TCF7L1	28512	36022	53375	46	53291
CSNK1G1-FSHB-FZD1	30998	2577	47731	11545	47835	FSHB-JUN-SENP2	8504	11359	1933	11062	13593
CSNK2A1-FSHB-LEF1	57055	1237	51589	12220	31790	CTBP2-FOXN1-FSHB	23856	40293	23082	53127	1837
FSHB-LEF1-SLC9A3R1	34110	47269	1903	15643	45779	APC-FSHB-LEF1	56896	21413	52867	5217	28793
DIXDC1-FSHB-TCF7L1	13822	52661	54003	3177	5869	FRZB-FSHB-LRP5	34073	16424	34151	9778	55580
FSHB-NKD1-WIF1	24095	15522	18330	7234	28767	FSHB-GSK3A-WNT5A	3423	15383	30952	30779	42858
DIXDC1-FSHB-SFRP4	13901	35834	56885	9145	10625	CCND1-CTNBP1-FSHB	10903	57067	84	14969	9086
FSHB-MYC-WNT4	29072	10195	10094	2456	2568	DVL1-FSHB-FZD1	3557	48584	50929	1986	26905
FRZB-FSHB-PPP2CA	18947	29614	39286	5288	45027	EP300-FOXN1-FSHB	2802	1330	33722	46172	2708
FSHB-JUN-WNT4	52891	1241	4783	6486	15806	CSNK1G1-FSHB-LRP5	47118	5185	21879	18285	54603
CSNK1G1-FSHB-RHOU	47722	23571	41553	10002	20180	FSHB-JUN-TCF7	7804	30904	565	20582	2501
FSHB-FZD2-NKD1	17626	47853	2527	46929	13014	FSHB-PYGO1-WNT2	5673	7061	3497	1837	50147
CSNK1G1-FSHB-WNT2	50502	3033	48214	9696	46010	FSHB-LEF1-MYC	10894	16685	5708	19074	53792
FSHB-MYC-RHOU	13055	25852	10079	20516	29919	FSHB-NKD1-NLK	28359	8433	16880	40917	24813
FSHB-PYGO1-WNT3A	9583	23325	1231	22957	44849	DAAMI-FOXN1-FSHB	2820	39084	4512	44503	45
FBXW2-FSHB-FZD2	9636	32142	51450	29379	5217	CCND1-CTBP1-FSHB	36917	56532	211	43826	268
FSHB-JUN-LRP5	56899	1565	391	32348	8019	CSNK1D-CTNBP1-FSHB	15509	42611	40	44944	2520

Table 2: Rankings of FSHB-X-X. A list of approximately first 125 combinations with rankings below 10,000 out of 57,155. SA - HSIC; Kernel - rbf

TCFDN attenuated GnRH regulation of CGA promoter activity, a known downstream target of JUN. Together, their results indicated that GnRH regulation of JUN transcription required a functional interaction between TCF/LEF and β -catenin and that

RANKING @ t_i USING SOBOL - 2002

3rd order comb.	t_1	t_3	t_6	t_{12}	t_{24}	3rd order comb.	t_1	t_3	t_6	t_{12}	t_{24}
FSHB-T-WNT5A	45606	52982	44145	47718	206	FSHB-NKD1-PPP2R1A	46297	55865	50849	48169	20237
FSHB-FZD2-SENP2	14802	30771	22388	3404	40748	FSHB-FZD2-WNT4	25678	24971	11443	1797	54089
FSHB-FZD2-PPP2R1A	42041	22925	48680	43398	7266	FSHB-FZD2-FZD7	26959	9124	25425	27104	51165
FSHB-T-WNT4	11538	4148	13011	9461	56946	FSHB-FZD2-KREMEN1	36466	29558	45780	49639	2209
FSHB-FZD2-TLE2	33626	22410	36622	44597	5789	FSHB-FZD2-LRP5	37430	4447	36334	42191	461
FSHB-T-TLE2	50581	47580	41050	44717	6365	FSHB-FZD2-SFRP4	24793	159	20235	23554	52209
FSHB-NKD1-TLE2	44409	50330	45264	42198	2365	CSNK2A1-FSHB-SFRP4	44409	50330	45264	42198	2365
CSNK1G1-FSHB-LEF1	38254	27148	47701	53981	4899	FSHB-LEF1-TCF7L1	53380	46700	43154	45016	3811
CSNK1D-FSHB-LEF1	17557	28861	26741	15958	23463	FSHB-NKD1-SENP2	15201	10828	10232	10064	44517
CSNK1G1-FSHB-SFRP4	49169	3805	44567	32085	3551	FSHB-T-TCF7	12530	4398	19772	3483	56001
DKK1-FSHB-SENP2	25567	47671	11467	15785	31909	FSHB-FZD2-FZD6	38240	48926	38881	51310	3907
FSHB-NKD1-WNT2B	44401	54732	42873	52925	7821	FSHB-LEF1-TLE2	37682	32014	41063	48638	11596
DIXDC1-FSHB-LEF1	48274	9621	43078	41675	11440	FSHB-GSK3A-KREMEN1	49626	22553	37390	51741	6459
FSHB-FZD2-PPP2CA	15048	34207	8473	13799	49835	FSHB-FZD2-TCF7L1	37685	39471	39763	47879	9857
FSHB-NKD1-RHOU	45675	10162	48275	54199	600	FSHB-NKD1-SFRP1	41925	46232	46892	47087	12907
FRZB-FSHB-SENP2	16157	4030	19992	6634	56588	FSHB-FZD2-TCF7	19405	17860	17389	9333	47198
FSHB-T-TCF7L1	44655	52790	37387	53692	1142	CSNK1G1-FSHB-SENP2	47318	7617	44202	35329	27387
FSHB-GSK3A-SENP2	25073	23609	16769	2541	50098	FSHB-FZD2-LEF1	19669	52700	20759	14981	56680
FSHB-NKD1-WNT5A	37314	18350	48369	53041	3700	FSHB-FZD2-WNT5A	31407	32496	45697	55367	3033
FRZB-FSHB-SFRP4	22547	28880	15534	5781	54893	FSHB-LEF1-SENP2	20816	17194	23144	10318	20084
FSHB-FZD2-GSK3B	36995	43609	40351	47460	771	FSHB-NKD1-TCF7L1	46622	3458	47720	55073	7419
FSHB-T-WNT2	24211	1414	17304	8880	46716	CSNK1G1-FSHB-PPP2CA	45864	55377	47231	36646	7302
DKK1-FSHB-LRP5	52206	8595	49363	38360	14056	FSHB-NKD1-TCF7	10577	53765	9421	2083	49699
CSNK2A1-FSHB-PPP2CA	8916	2500	542	374	35437	FSHB-FZD2-FBXW4	32337	56996	36896	33580	4837
CSNK2A1-FSHB-WNT2B	56035	49999	49902	45966	16417	FSHB-MYC-SENP2	34577	39415	36987	50908	21809
FSHB-FZD2-FZD8	30146	48105	31743	30062	5911	FSHB-FZD2-PITX2	21425	53181	12066	7803	49923
FSHB-FZD2-SLC9A3R1	19200	4040	13902	8297	52702	FSHB-FZD2-TLE1	23403	34171	20528	12597	51251
FSHB-LEF1-WNT4	8288	8012	27212	12914	53835	FSHB-FZD2-RHOU	40361	54590	45165	48229	8430
FSHB-T-WNT3A	38613	13069	34339	29636	16201	FSHB-GSK3A-PPP2R1A	49293	47302	38519	53839	5159
FSHB-FZD2-WNT3A	39818	41432	46903	36007	7232	CSNK1D-FGF4-FSHB	37586	23188	30054	39574	14949
FSHB-NKD1-WNT2	12767	2441	14264	4232	49363	FSHB-FZD2-SFRP1	42237	26313	34781	53766	16282
CSNK2A1-FSHB-FZD7	3089	7692	3943	5213	55917	FSHB-GSK3A-FBXW4	34329	15925	36450	37139	20017
FZD5-FSHB-SENP2	633	33986	20942	7747	44880	FSHB-GSK3A-RHOU	45642	17663	41834	54441	6142
FSHB-FZD2-PORCN	35693	3921	45087	49396	7163	FSHB-MYC-TLE2	5624	43156	26678	3876	41523
AES-FOXN1-FSHB	14879	14406	21545	28470	35799	FSHB-MYC-FBXW4	12489	410	5555	4473	45473
CSNK1G1-FSHB-MYC	10008	29873	20279	26881	48302	FSHB-FZD2-NLK	39610	21989	44077	55924	5573
DIXDC1-FSHB-FZD1	26998	49234	15449	5156	42294	FBXW11-FOXN1-FSHB	13893	972	8905	24278	43530
DIXDC1-FSHB-T	13832	55402	22848	25333	31832	CSNK1G1-FSHB-WNT2B	6562	41743	11739	18943	50322
FSHB-PORCN-PPP2R1A	18030	38591	13363	21618	36386	CSNK2A1-FSHB-FZD1	46615	46448	50771	45908	17553
FSHB-GSK3A-WNT2B	48028	21079	39770	54047	108	CSNK2A1-FSHB-SENP2	10122	25267	392	2416	51870
CSNK1G1-FSHB-T	6318	9942	3904	6835	49975	FOSL1-FOXN1-FSHB	52272	52961	47841	48448	6873
FSHB-NKD1-FBXW4	50332	51183	48187	53103	1776	CSNK1G1-FSHB-TLE2	9414	4880	3042	17235	46900
FRZB-FSHB-FZD1	34981	44066	44219	48500	19494	FSHB-FZD2-WNT2	20119	1545	8398	8195	47086
FSHB-GSK3A-TCF7	8455	45500	24853	24609	48135	FSHB-FZD2-MYC	35859	43204	43101	46685	1825
BCL9-FGF4-FSHB	25858	55226	9349	11632	40519	FSHB-LEF1-SFRP4	16564	3256	12981	10830	46159
FSHB-T-TLE1	6555	9725	16125	12462	50757	FRZB-FSHB-LEF1	15029	8446	17525	5382	55559
CSNK1G1-FSHB-TCF7L1	12488	10887	22163	26387	56316	CSNK2A1-FSHB-TCF7L1	55973	47958	56151	46957	1597
CSNK1G1-FSHB-FZD1	24433	37249	2369	970	55669	FSHB-JUN-SENP2	32679	30532	35042	31189	25190
CSNK2A1-FSHB-LEF1	23163	9325	3502	903	40947	CTBP2-FOXN1-FSHB	16954	33144	5169	7776	31645
FSHB-LEF1-SLC9A3R1	16211	667	11207	1711	11374	APC-FSHB-LEF1	24825	28397	7342	26962	47852
DIXDC1-FSHB-TCF7L1	13088	35355	12050	12107	48417	FRZB-FSHB-LRP5	42138	48646	39624	51762	1587
FSHB-NKD1-WIF1	8501	17679	24446	9809	47619	FSHB-GSK3A-WNT5A	34115	22730	34862	34229	6583
DIXDC1-FSHB-SFRP4	43759	10428	41256	50399	21035	CCND1-CTNNBIP1-FSHB	7276	1695	18768	9309	38472
FSHB-MYC-WNT4	49552	51232	29648	44020	1277	DVL1-FSHB-FZD1	53095	6814	34492	47594	17971
FRZB-FSHB-PPP2CA	14018	18181	26398	14257	47110	EP300-FOXN1-FSHB	35241	7329	47007	37898	866
FSHB-JUN-WNT4	31925	36849	32780	30893	15816	CSNK1G1-FSHB-LRP5	12455	9403	1259	14891	34561
CSNK1G1-FSHB-RHOU	9813	49729	12944	21779	29733	FSHB-JUN-TCF7	35950	22514	33093	33203	2559
FSHB-FZD2-NKD1	17455	35178	13079	1237	51503	FSHB-PYGO1-WNT2	36180	17062	38506	54729	31672
CSNK1G1-FSHB-WNT2	50988	43343	56638	51283	7336	FSHB-LEF1-MYC	48994	47927	41761	50026	35523
FSHB-MYC-RHOU	22500	17661	20158	6240	35404	FSHB-NKD1-NLK	37330	45271	47731	49313	26243
FSHB-PYGO1-WNT3A	12428	4924	26907	10415	56360	DAAMI-FOXN1-FSHB	6991	42829	15581	2290	54407
FBXW2-FSHB-FZD2	26485	9037	9070	9927	55287	CCND1-CTBP1-FSHB	37568	8258	40598	32419	20977
FSHB-JUN-LRP5	23341	38818	22426	24943	26228	CSNK1D-CTNNBIP1-FSHB	19041	22179	27128	25108	26024

Table 3: Rankings of FSHB-X-X. A list of approximately first 125 combinations with rankings below 10,000 out of 57,155. SA - SOBOL; Implementation - 2002

alteration of either impacted expression of JUN downstream targets such as CGA.

Looking at the tables above, one finds the following combinations for JUN along with FSHB, to be prominent at 3rd order level - FSHB-JUN-WNT4, FSHB-JUN-LRP5,

RANKING @ t_i USING SOBOL - MARTINEZ

3rd order comb.	t_1	t_3	t_6	t_{12}	t_{24}	3rd order comb.	t_1	t_3	t_6	t_{12}	t_{24}
FSHB-T-WNT5A	56577	45398	1560	25202	8403	FSHB-NKD1-PPP2R1A	53109	51767	230	25045	9445
FSHB-FZD2-SENP2	4678	20262	6383	27755	44142	FSHB-FZD2-WNT4	2021	57140	14789	29295	53443
FSHB-FZD2-PPP2R1A	46195	47198	3580	18156	8533	FSHB-FZD2-FZD7	4202	26935	6525	7758	55877
FSHB-T-WNT4	40510	47251	23497	18487	55763	FSHB-FZD2-KREMEN1	45395	27154	3148	15559	7265
FSHB-FZD2-TLE2	23273	14562	92	20787	10216	FSHB-FZD2-LRP5	43130	48404	22498	7991	7900
FSHB-T-TLE2	45245	47204	17472	39734	9372	FSHB-FZD2-SFRP4	2797	53565	8951	1619	56167
FSHB-NKD1-TLE2	45128	54511	27034	495	9751	CSNK2A1-FSHB-SFRP4	6990	46178	45901	7793	15573
CSNK1G1-FSHB-LEF1	8757	48545	39614	32449	13625	FSHB-LEF1-TCF7L1	54835	54755	37	17373	8512
CSNK1D-FSHB-LEF1	19222	39228	21058	21493	6562	FSHB-NKD1-SENP2	26326	50101	3632	18950	54806
CSNK1G1-FSHB-SFRP4	39476	50249	41873	33694	14579	FSHB-T-TCF7	28710	20364	21729	24657	54755
DKK1-FSHB-SENP2	1237	22131	34620	28281	43154	FSHB-FZD2-FZD6	42102	50194	2020	14283	8347
FSHB-NKD1-WNT2B	55721	42851	2627	5107	7553	FSHB-LEF1-TLE2	39229	56246	22915	14177	9540
DIXDC1-FSHB-LEF1	36469	12003	5172	34968	35203	FSHB-GSK3A-KREMEN1	43085	48197	16908	5349	9023
FSHB-FZD2-PPP2CA	20341	18178	13864	46410	55298	FSHB-FZD2-TCF7L1	35393	47549	22879	8461	9497
FSHB-NKD1-RHOU	55892	43953	469	18180	10414	FSHB-NKD1-SFRP1	28002	16077	279	14622	6815
FRZB-FSHB-SENP2	39025	16786	12898	8014	29180	FSHB-FZD2-TCF7	5540	55593	21539	11167	52305
FSHB-T-TCF7L1	55749	44728	4194	5153	7127	CSNK1G1-FSHB-SENP2	32972	50887	28581	8306	20113
FSHB-GSK3A-SENP2	7731	54453	20490	20338	36146	FSHB-FZD2-LEF1	6781	32231	34450	14806	52631
FSHB-NKD1-WNT5A	54779	40235	14719	3551	9105	FSHB-FZD2-WNT5A	22760	56612	24534	7272	7730
FRZB-FSHB-SFRP4	5598	20151	11145	1391	47743	FSHB-LEF1-SENP2	110	43538	5716	50939	40396
FSHB-FZD2-GSK3B	38333	51758	2822	14124	8093	FSHB-NKD1-TCF7L1	46897	40396	1839	679	7727
FSHB-T-WNT2	16121	52728	21962	20850	50241	CSNK1G1-FSHB-PPP2CA	40612	43508	22826	3439	25861
DKK1-FSHB-LRP5	18267	14160	7841	7776	28947	FSHB-NKD1-TCF7	32538	48825	14879	5232	4084
CSNK2A1-FSHB-PPP2CA	18252	39529	48641	45395	6382	FSHB-FZD2-FBXW4	29744	53466	4242	198	7263
CSNK2A1-FSHB-WNT2B	57093	25886	24846	4769	8081	FSHB-MYC-SENP2	20459	24295	68	18425	9142
FSHB-FZD2-FZD8	20555	51232	8169	16551	7285	FSHB-FZD2-PITX2	1274	54630	28998	48951	32890
FSHB-FZD2-SLC9A3R1	16717	52624	4125	46204	53856	FSHB-FZD2-TLE1	537	22601	4732	51181	46554
FSHB-LEF1-WNT4	15442	25307	14632	33427	52184	FSHB-FZD2-RHOU	48503	50300	18409	3241	10967
FSHB-T-WNT3A	43678	43564	11912	21619	8516	FSHB-GSK3A-PPP2R1A	37883	32032	13437	29910	10314
FSHB-FZD2-WNT3A	30517	55741	54	3890	8435	CSNK1D-FGF4-FSHB	53386	36653	4663	24262	56290
FSHB-NKD1-WNT2	4151	11327	17224	21348	50813	FSHB-FZD2-SFRP1	38204	33365	18256	9764	9537
CSNK2A1-FSHB-FZD7	6856	18689	18850	39695	45801	FSHB-GSK3A-FBXW4	28672	39455	5440	19463	16542
FZD5-FSHB-SENP2	48811	54911	6976	34025	5862	FSHB-GSK3A-RHOU	56076	30316	9478	10986	7651
FSHB-FZD2-PORCN	42224	53610	34007	22178	13564	FSHB-MYC-TLE2	22055	49016	11812	1709	1042
AES-FOXN1-FSHB	35919	16555	8060	25389	55192	FSHB-MYC-FBXW4	22119	28249	1860	11029	54094
CSNK1G1-FSHB-MYC	16803	10241	15398	7414	1214	FSHB-FZD2-NLK	40955	45035	3571	2400	7322
DIXDC1-FSHB-FZD1	26861	25469	5480	18666	9251	FBXW11-FOXN1-FSHB	18269	21435	20004	7133	34182
DIXDC1-FSHB-T	314	15562	3544	12886	50313	CSNK1G1-FSHB-WNT2B	24679	21316	37424	4944	42965
FSHB-PORCN-PPP2R1A	32332	26578	54925	38162	421	CSNK2A1-FSHB-FZD1	34430	14822	30557	7690	18794
FSHB-GSK3A-WNT2B	48093	22365	4365	21073	7319	CSNK2A1-FSHB-SENP2	2358	42213	17814	39177	55018
CSNK1G1-FSHB-T	25656	40734	22557	25924	2702	FOSL1-FOXN1-FSHB	26149	40026	43592	11204	19356
FSHB-NKD1-FBXW4	56274	37325	2275	13039	8834	CSNK1G1-FSHB-TLE2	27601	12818	25650	12730	19133
FRZB-FSHB-FZD1	23069	46224	4839	22497	15204	FSHB-FZD2-WNT2	18975	44801	1911	16194	51161
FSHB-GSK3A-TCF7	34798	10844	9167	11594	55415	FSHB-FZD2-MYC	38351	55407	6447	11632	8130
BCL9-FGF4-FSHB	2112	7711	37537	37717	47676	FSHB-LEF1-SFRP4	18018	39380	17200	41636	49561
FSHB-T-TLE1	50050	36189	19330	45932	52109	FRZB-FSHB-LEF1	32782	17175	9329	6311	40454
CSNK1G1-FSHB-TCF7L1	15343	15356	28915	7962	8727	CSNK2A1-FSHB-TCF7L1	47175	44476	22845	44711	15604
CSNK1G1-FSHB-FZD1	12150	43310	18600	17184	9181	FSHB-JUN-SENP2	31128	45450	45679	41565	8582
CSNK2A1-FSHB-LEF1	2869	54364	39557	33239	582	CTBP2-FOXN1-FSHB	37991	31039	12067	20052	53154
FSHB-LEF1-SLC9A3R1	18360	46515	1500	14894	53508	APC-FSHB-LEF1	1801	9627	13790	14031	42039
DIXDC1-FSHB-TCF7L1	9362	46730	21740	20294	47583	FRZB-FSHB-LRP5	53839	40293	8638	32918	15552
FSHB-NKD1-WIF1	14017	26546	32668	27446	43796	FSHB-GSK3A-WNT5A	36948	46381	47772	40630	8149
DIXDC1-FSHB-SFRP4	39328	6455	29637	32004	30835	CCND1-CTNNBIP1-FSHB	3988	29932	4093	17809	17442
FSHB-MYC-WNT4	56128	47496	13258	1139	24357	DVL1-FSHB-FZD1	18268	11282	34081	39549	29022
FRZB-FSHB-PPP2CA	19994	29788	20561	7472	13303	EP300-FOXN1-FSHB	49686	23243	20068	55297	13265
FSHB-JUN-WNT4	28275	32727	37186	31196	7026	CSNK1G1-FSHB-LRP5	36847	3305	35090	30551	32926
CSNK1G1-FSHB-RHOU	5063	21037	36196	18467	3637	FSHB-JUN-TCF7	46106	37157	41914	40666	7402
FSHB-FZD2-NKD1	17654	13500	6649	12575	54948	FSHB-PYGO1-WNT2	51860	26915	2338	1488	15040
CSNK1G1-FSHB-WNT2	53602	28689	40967	37725	32991	FSHB-LEF1-MYC	55596	49274	3567	14390	8376
FSHB-MYC-RHOU	921	13552	8453	50669	49781	FSHB-NKD1-NLK	50848	46282	2144	11725	12197
FSHB-PYGO1-WNT3A	25604	14793	12978	17819	41000	DAAMI-FOXN1-FSHB	28778	2372	39817	56157	49836
FBXW2-FSHB-FZD2	27096	42506	14040	53304	6091	CCND1-CTBP1-FSHB	8924	46188	8725	26829	11335
FSHB-JUN-LRP5	7727	12480	53014	37278	36405	CSNK1D-CTNNBIP1-FSHB	24245	40522	48625	2440	18316

Table 4: Rankings of FSHB-X-X. A list of approximately first 125 combinations with rankings below 10,000 out of 57,155. SA - SOBOL; Implementation - martinez

FSHB-JUN-SENP2 and FSHB-JUN-TCF7.

Looking at the tables above, one finds the following combinations for members of TCF family along with FSHB, to be prominent at 3rd order level - FSHB-T-TCF7L1,

FSHB-GSK3A-TCF7, CSNK1G1-FSHB-TCF7L1, DIXDC1-FSHB-TCF7L1, FSHB-LEF1-TCF7L1, FSHB-T-TCF7, FSHB-FZD2-TCF7L1, FSHB-FZD2-TCF7, FSHB-NKD1-TCF7L1, FSHB-NKD1-TCF7, CSNK2A1-FSHB-TCF7L1 and FSHB-JUN-TCF7.

Looking at the tables above, one finds the following combinations for LEF1 along with FSHB, to be prominent at 3rd order level - CSNK1G1-FSHB-LEF1, CSNK1D-FSHB-LEF1, DIXDC1-FSHB-LEF1, FSHB-LEF1-WNT4, CSNK2A1-FSHB-LEF1, FSHB-LEF1-SLC9A3R1, FSHB-LEF1-TCF7L1, FSHB-LEF1-TLE2, FSHB-FZD2-LEF1, FSHB-LEF1-SEN2, FSHB-LEF1-SFRP4, FRZB-FSHB-LEF1, APC-FSHB-LEF1 and FSHB-LEF1-MYC.

Looking at the tables above, one finds the following combinations for CTNNBIP1 along with FSHB, to be prominent at 3rd order level - CCND1-CTNNBIP1-FSHB and CSNK1D-CTNNBIP1-FSHB.

All these combinations indicate the existence of a possible synergy when they take a higher rank in the list of combinations.

6.3.3. Examining the behaviour of FOX-FSHB-X combinations

Activins regulate selective synthesis and release of FSH from pituitary gonadotropes. They directly stimulate murine Fshb subunit gene transcription through a consensus 8-bp Sma- and Mad-related protein-binding element (SBE) in the proximal promoter. In contrast, the human FSHB promoter is relatively insensitive to the direct effects of activins and lacks this SBE. Lamba et al. [19] determined the mechanisms mediating differential activin induction of human, porcine, and murine Fshb/FSHB promoters. They mapped an activin response element in the proximal porcine promoter and identified interspecies variation in a single base pair in close proximity that conferred strong binding of the forkhead transcription factor FOXL2 to the porcine, but not human or murine, promoters. Introduction of the human base pair into the porcine promoter abolished FOXL2 binding and activin A induction. FOXL2 conferred activin A induction to the porcine promoter in heterologous cells, whereas knockdown of the endogenous protein in gonadotropes inhibited the activin A response. The murine Fshb promoter lacked the high-affinity FOXL2-binding site, but its activin induction was FOXL2 sensitive. Further, they identified a more proximal FOXL2-binding element in the murine promoter, which is conserved across species. They observed that mutation of this site attenuated activin A induction of both the porcine and murine promoters. Collectively, their data indicated a novel role for FOXL2 in activin A-regulated FSHB transcription.

Looking at the tables above, one finds the following combinations for members of FOX family along with FSHB, to be prominent at 3rd order level - AES-FOXN1-FSHB, FBXW11-FOXN1-FSHB, FOXL1-FOXN1-FSHB, CTBP2-FOXN1-FSHB, EP300-FOXN1-FSHB and DAAM1-FOXN1-FSHB.

7. Conclusion

This manuscript studies the time behaviour of 3rd order combinations of FSHB in WNT3A stimulated HEK 293 cells. Based on the established 2nd order combinations of the FSHB, 3rd order combinations emerge using the machine learning based search

engine. These 3rd order combinations might be of interest for further wet lab investigations.

Competing interests

No competing interest is declared.

Author contributions statement

SS conceived and designed the experiments; wrote the code; performed the experiments; analyzed the data; wrote the manuscript.

Availability of code

Code for time series data available at CERN based Zenodo on <https://zenodo.org/records/14637456>.

Acknowledgments

Special thanks to Mrs. Rita Sinha and late Mr. Prabhat Sinha for supporting the author financially, without which this work could not have been made possible.

Supplementary

The following files (ending with .txt and can be opened in R or in simple text processing program) with these names are made available with this manuscript. For FSHB, (1) **-3-odr-TP-ranking-linear.txt**, (2) **-3-odr-TP-ranking-rbf.txt**, (3) **-3-odr-TP-ranking-2002.txt**, and (4) **-3-odr-TP-ranking-martinez.txt**, contain rankings for 3rd order combinations across each time point for, HSIC (linear kernel), HSIC (rbf kernel), SOBOL (2002 implementation) and SOBOL (martinez implementation), respectively.

References

- [1] T. S. Gujral, G. MacBeath, A system-wide investigation of the dynamics of wnt signaling reveals novel phases of transcriptional regulation, *PloS one* 5 (2010) e10024.
- [2] S. Sinha, Machine learning ranking of plausible (un) explored synergistic gene combinations using sensitivity indices of time series measurements of wnt signaling pathway, *Integrative Biology* 16 (2024) zya020.
- [3] T. Joachims, Training linear svms in linear time, in: *Proceedings of the 12th ACM SIGKDD international conference on Knowledge discovery and data mining*, ACM, 2006, pp. 217–226.
- [4] S. Standring, *Gray's Anatomy: The Anatomical Basis of Clinical Practice*, Gray's Anatomy Series, Elsevier Limited, 2016. URL: <https://books.google.co.in/books?id=LjP9rQEACAAJ>.

- [5] C. Cahoreau, D. Klett, Y. Combarous, Structure–function relationships of glycoprotein hormones and their subunits ancestors, *Frontiers in endocrinology* 6 (2015) 26.
- [6] P. C. Watkins, R. EDDY, A. K. BECK, V. VELLUCCI, B. LEVERONE, R. E. TANZI, J. F. GUSELLA, T. B. SHOWS, Dna sequence and regional assignment of the human follicle-stimulating hormone β -subunit gene to the short arm of human chromosome 11, *Dna* 6 (1987) 205–212.
- [7] X. Jiang, H. Liu, X. Chen, P.-H. Chen, D. Fischer, V. Sriraman, H. N. Yu, S. Arkininstall, X. He, Structure of follicle-stimulating hormone in complex with the entire ectodomain of its receptor, *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 109 (2012) 12491–12496.
- [8] A. Ulloa-Aguirre, T. Zariñán, A. M. Pasapera, P. Casas-González, J. A. Dias, Multiple facets of follicle-stimulating hormone receptor function, *Endocrine* 32 (2007) 251–263.
- [9] Y.-X. Tao, D. L. Segaloff, Follicle stimulating hormone receptor mutations and reproductive disorders, *Progress in molecular biology and translational science* 89 (2009) 115–131.
- [10] M. Simoni, J. Gromoll, E. Nieschlag, The follicle-stimulating hormone receptor: biochemistry, molecular biology, physiology, and pathophysiology, *Endocrine reviews* 18 (1997) 739–773.
- [11] S. Sinha, Hilbert-schmidt and sobol sensitivity indices for static and time series wnt signaling measurements in colorectal cancer-part a, *BMC systems biology* 11 (2017) 120.
- [12] S. Da Veiga, Global sensitivity analysis with dependence measures, *Journal of Statistical Computation and Simulation* 85 (2015) 1283–1305.
- [13] A. Saltelli, Making best use of model evaluations to compute sensitivity indices, *Computer physics communications* 145 (2002) 280–297.
- [14] J. Martinez, Analyse de sensibilité globale par decomposition de la variance, Presentation in Journée des GdR Ondes & Mascot 13 (2011) 207.
- [15] M. Baudin, K. Boumhaout, T. Delage, B. Iooss, J.-M. Martinez, Numerical stability of sobol’indices estimation formula, in: *Proceedings of the 8th International Conference on Sensitivity Analysis of Model Output (SAMO 2016)*, volume 30, 2016, pp. 50–51.
- [16] D. J. Bernard, J. Fortin, Y. Wang, P. Lamba, Mechanisms of fsh synthesis: what we know, what we don’t, and why you should care, *Fertility and sterility* 93 (2010) 2465–2485.
- [17] A. J. Mason, J. S. Hayflick, R. T. Zoeller, W. S. Young III, H. S. Phillips, K. Nikolics, P. H. Seeburg, A deletion truncating the gonadotropin-releasing hormone gene is responsible for hypogonadism in the hpg mouse, *Science* 234 (1986) 1366–1371.
- [18] T. B. Salisbury, A. K. Binder, J. C. Grammer, J. H. Nilson, GnRH-regulated expression of jun and jun target genes in gonadotropes requires a functional interaction between tcf/lef family members and β -catenin, *Molecular endocrinology* 23 (2009) 402–411.
- [19] P. Lamba, J. Fortin, S. Tran, Y. Wang, D. J. Bernard, A novel role for the forkhead transcription factor foxl2 in activin a-regulated follicle-stimulating hormone β subunit transcription, *Molecular Endocrinology* 23 (2009) 1001–1013.